

The Influence of Customer Value on Brand Evangelism: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Customers from a Group of Restaurants in Mosul

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Abstract

The main purpose of the research is to verify the Influence of customer value, in its various forms (functional, emotional, and symbolic), on enhancing customer behaviors toward brand Evangelism (positive brand referral, Oppositional brand referral, and Intent to continue purchasing the brand). The current research used the descriptive-analytical approach to describe the research variables and the nature of the relationship between them. Primary data was collected using a questionnaire distributed to (79) customers receiving food service from three well-known restaurants (Hatab, Khattar, and Abu Laila) in Mosul city during the research period. The research hypotheses were tested using structural equation modeling. One of the most important findings of the study was the significant impact of functional and emotional value in motivating customers to speak positively about the restaurant and intend to continue dealing with them in the future.

Keywords: *Customer value, brand evangelism.*

JEL Classification codes: *L83, N3, P36.*

Suggested citation: Abdullah, A.A., Al-Abbasi, H.S., & Jassim, I.M. (2025). The Influence of Customer Value on Brand Evangelism: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Customers from a Group of Restaurants in Mosul. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(3), 95-111. DOI: 10.59324/ejmeb.2025.2(3).08

Introduction

Over the past decades, extensive research has been conducted on customer value creation across various service sectors, particularly hospitality. Providing diverse customer value in a highly competitive environment has become vital for food service organizations to maintain long-term relationships with their customers. Restaurants keen to achieve success in local markets work to create a distinct customer value proposition that can turn customers into brand evangelists (they speak positively about the restaurant and negatively about competing restaurants, and they intend to repeat dealing with the restaurant in the near future). Therefore, conducting this research on a group of customers who frequent restaurants in Mosul is necessary to identify the functional,

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emotional, and symbolic value elements that impress customers and motivate them to advocate for the restaurant. The primary objective of the research is to enhance current knowledge of the research variables and demonstrate how the comprehensive customer value propositions (functional, emotional, and symbolic) that restaurants offer their customers increase the momentum of brand evangelism. Theoretical literature will be utilized in a manner consistent with the nature of service provided by restaurants to their customers. Therefore, the question that guides this research is: To what extent do customer value types influence the types of evangelistic behavior for the customer's favorite restaurant brand?

Literature Review

The Concept of Customer Value

Many business organizations today are increasingly focused on customer value as a business approach and strategic direction for achieving excellence. This approach focuses on the customer, understanding their needs and desires, and providing them with a distinct value that motivates them to promote the organization's brand and intend to continue doing business with it (Al-Jabouri, 2013, 39). Customer value is defined as a positive, functional, emotional, and symbolic experience a customer receives when interacting with a service organization, fostering a positive attitude and an intention to continue doing business with the organization if needed in the future (Yieh & Jiun, 2012, 178).. It is also defined as the emotional bond formed between a customer and an organization as a result of benefiting from the service provided by the organization (Ganthika & Wahdiniwati, 2019, 111).

Sanchez & Iniesta (2009) described it as the customer's relative preference for service attributes, which are subjectively evaluated by the customer (Hasfarr et al., 2020, 87). The researchers provide an operational definition of customer value: Customer value is defined as the value of the functional, emotional, and symbolic benefits a customer receives from visiting one of the selected restaurants in Mosul city, compared to the costs the customer incurs in exchange for those benefits. These values are measured in a questionnaire developed for this purpose.

Types of Customer Value

Ke dwell, (2008) believes that the optimal marketing strategy based on customer value should focus on the functional, emotional, and symbolic aspects delivered to the customer, but to varying degrees depending on the customer's personality, perceptions, motivations, age, gender, and the type of service provided. In this context, (Kotler, 2012) asserts that customers evaluate three types of values when purchasing a product or service (Abdullah & Alwan, 2022, 43). These values are:

Functional Value

Functional value is based on the functional needs that drive consumers to seek out service offerings that satisfy those needs. Functional value is defined as the extent to which a service meets the customer's preferred characteristics in terms of service provider performance, quality, durability, and reliability (Sharmelly & Klarin, 2021, 3). It also refers to the extent to which the price and quality of a service align with the consumer's expected benefit, which is the satisfaction of their needs (Febriyanti & Irmawati, 2024, 177).

The functional value delivered to customers by restaurants includes the following;

- 1.Performance value is the value that shows the extent to which the service is able to meet the customer's needs. It is related to the quality of the food provided.
- 2.The appropriate price of the meal and the discounts offered, which save the customer money (Sabrina et al., 2023, 1807).

3. Offering a variety of foods.
4. Ease of access and convenient location.
5. Online ordering and delivery services are available 24/7 (Nazim, 2021,3).
6. Listening carefully to customer complaints to understand them and resolve them quickly.
7. The restaurant management apologizes to the customer and thanks them for filing the complaint, as a customer complaint can help the restaurant avoid future mistakes.
8. Follows up with the customer to ensure they are satisfied with the method of resolving the problem and eliminating its causes.
9. Speed of service provision and consistency of quality.
10. Exceptional attention to cleanliness.

People flock to McDonald's restaurants because of the quality of its food, and McDonald's maintains a high standard for what the organization calls "quality, cleanliness, and speed of service," compared to its competitors in local and global markets (Abdullah, 2011, p.7).

Emotional Value

Emotional values or benefits are based on emotional needs that drive customers to seek value propositions that satisfy those needs (Hisar, 2018, 178). With the decline in the functional competitive value of services, organizations began seeking to gain competitive advantage by differentiating their services by providing customers with emotional values (Rini & Absah, 2017, 69). Emotional values can highlight the fundamental differences between different brands if the functional values they offer are equal. Consumers rely on them to choose the appropriate alternative. They are difficult to imitate because they relate to the intangible aspects of the brand and are more attractive than functional values. They achieve distinction and value for the organization, particularly satisfaction, trust, and loyalty customers, as they strengthen deep emotional bonds between the customer and the organization. Emotional values refer to the positive feelings associated with the customer's use of a particular organization's services and may lead to loyalty (Lee et al., 2011, 686).

The emotional value propositions offered by restaurants include:

1. A conducive restaurant environment, competent service staff, and a positive service experience (Kovanoviene et al., 2021,62).
2. Safety and reassurance that the meal served by the restaurant, or ordered through the restaurant's website, is safe for human consumption and meets the specifications advertised by the restaurant on its social media accounts (Su, 2021,36).
3. Trust, the subjective belief that the restaurant will fulfill its commitment as the customer understands them (Pedreno & Garcia, 2022, 54).
4. The customer does not feel exploited and feels cared for by the restaurant.
5. Staff members treat customers with kindness, friendliness, and respect (Al-Jabouri, 2013, 74).

Symbolic Value

Symbolic value is the most subjective of all types of values. Symbolic value is defined as a combination of social benefits (related to the customer's relationship with others) and self-related benefits that an organization provides to the customer and enhance their self-image and social standing. It primarily relates to symbolic needs (the customer's need for identity) or social needs, such as social meaning, which typically depends on the perceptions of third parties with a special

connection to the customer (Nicholson, 2021, 118). Symbolic benefits are not simply part of the product's appearance, but rather reflect a variety of meanings and associations specific to the individual's self or their relationship with the social environment to which they belong or in which they live (Kovanoviene et al., 2021, 62).

Brand Evangelism

The Concept of Brand Evangelism

The concept of brand evangelism was introduced by (McConnell et al.) in their book, *Building Customer evangelists* (Menon & Shir, 2023, 1760). The term "evangelism" is derived from the Greek verb "kerusso," meaning "to announce," and is widely used in religious contexts to describe the dissemination of religious beliefs. A evangelist informs others of the good news of their beliefs. Similarly, in a business context, brand evangelists act as enthusiastic promoters of a brand, spreading positive word of mouth, defending it against criticism, and sharing their positive experiences with others (family, friends, and colleagues) (Ledisi & Harcourt, 2023, 6). Terms such as brand evangelists, champions, inspired consumers, advocates, brand fanatics, volunteer salespeople, customer messengers, and brand ambassadors, which can be found in the marketing literature, are similar in content and connotations. However, brand evangelists possess a strong psychological and emotional commitment to their preferred brand or service provider (Arkonsuo et al., 2014, 5).

Communication by evangelists can also be considered "preaching" in an attempt to convert others to consume or benefit from a brand. Brand evangelism is a term commonly used in marketing to describe customers' support and loyalty to a particular brand. This term refers to customers who become enthusiastic advocates, voluntarily promoting their preferred brand and influencing others to support it (Menon & Shir, 2023, 1760). (Metzler et al. (2007) defined brand evangelism as the commitment to disseminating positive information or opinions about a brand consumed by specific individuals, called brand evangelists, who are enthusiastic about their preferred brand in order to influence the consumption behavior of others and persuade them to purchase it (Rehman et al., 2022, 493).

It is defined as a strong relationship between a customer who has a strong emotional attachment to their favorite brand. (Becerra and Badrinarayanan, 2013) defined it as "active behavioral support for a brand, including actions such as purchasing the preferred brand, spreading positive word of mouth or content about it, and persuading others about it" (El-Naghi et al., 2023, 394). The researchers provide an operational definition of brand evangelism: a customer's strong relationship with their favorite restaurant and their commitment to spreading positive information about it to others to persuade them to visit the restaurant and benefit from its services. They are also willing to speak negatively about competing restaurants, are willing to defend the restaurant against negative talk about the restaurant, and are intent on continuing to do business with it in the short term.

Comparison between Word of Mouth (WOM) and Brand Evangelism

Swimberg et al. (2014) argue that brand evangelism is an advanced form of positive word-of-mouth advertising, or an extension of word-of-mouth. It is a behavior that involves defending a preferred brand against competing brands. Therefore, unlike word-of-mouth, which involves providing positive recommendations about the brand, brand evangelism focuses on speaking on behalf of the brand and convincing others to convert them into regular buyers of the preferred brand. It results from a long-term relationship between the customer and the brand. In other words, brand evangelism is a relationship-based behavior, whereas positive, transactional word-of-mouth

behavior occurs due to a short-term state of mind, particularly satisfaction. Therefore, positive word-of-mouth may disappear during a service failure or may transform into negative word-of-mouth (David, 2022, 6). While (Metzler et al. 2007) assumed that customers who spread positive word of mouth about brands they like, spread only positive opinions about them, (Nkoulou et al. 2022) confirmed that brand evangelism leads to a more effective response from customers (real loyalty), compared to positive word of mouth (brand satisfaction) (Shang, Y. & Li, F., 2024, 3).

Brand Evangelism Behaviors

Brand evangelism was defined by researchers (Becerra & Badrinarayanan, 2013) as three important behaviors: (positive brand referral, Oppositional brand referral, and Intent to continue purchasing the brand) (El-Naghi et al., 2023, 395). These are dimensions of brand evangelism.

Positive Brand Referral

Becerra & Badrinarayanan, (2013) defined positive brand referral as a customer's tendency to engage in communication with other consumers about that organization. (Matzler et al. 2007) asserted that when a customer engages with an organization on a consistent basis, they develop an emotional connection with it and speak positively about it to other consumers. Therefore, positive brand referral is the tendency to provide positive information about the organization (El-Naghi et al., 2023, 395). In a related context, positive brand referral is one of the most valuable resources consumers can leverage to make better decisions, as consumers prefer to obtain information from more personal sources, such as family members, friends, or people with expertise around them (Elgahwash, 2024, 91).

Oppositional Brand Referral

A customer who is an advocate tends to view their preferred organization as unlike any other, even though they share the same characteristics and benefits. The customer exhibits anti-competitive behavior and provides unfavorable information about the competitor (El-Naghi et al., 2023, 395). (Sundaram & Webster, 1998) suggest that when customers have an emotional connection with an organization, they will express themselves as supporters of the organization and tend to spread negative opinions about the competitor (Riorini, 2015, 34).

Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is a customer's continued use of a particular organization's services in the future when they perceive the organization's value. (Che et al. 2017) defined purchase intention as a high desire to re-engage with an organization that provides a service in the very near future (El-Naghi et al., 2023, 395). Customers who have a strong attachment to an organization tend to demonstrate higher transaction intentions compared to those who are not evangelists with the organization's brand (Bethe & Jean, 2022, 47). Interest in purchasing or utilizing a service can be achieved when criteria are consistent with customer desires (Bougeanville & Ruswanti, 2017, 13). Purchase intention can be described as a customer's desire or interest to purchase a particular service in the near future. Interest and desire to purchase arise from the customer's confidence in the service coupled with the ability to purchase (Roring et al., 2024, 166). Purchase intention is a form of Real customer loyalty that reflects the strong functional and emotional relationship between the customer and the preferred service organization (Bernarto et al., 2024, 5).

Review of Previous Studies

Studies Related to Customer Value

The results of a study by (Pedreno & Garcia, 2022) revealed that customer value fundamentally influences the intention to purchase from an organization. The results of a study by (Sabrina et al.,

2023) that surveyed a sample of (100) customers over the age of (17) revealed the impact of customer value on customer satisfaction. The study (Hasfar et al, 2020) aimed to explore the impact of customer value and customer experience on customer satisfaction and loyalty to the organization. The study surveyed the opinions of (80) customers of Meratus Company. The results of the study achieved its aim. The study ((Ganthika & Wahdiniwaty, 2019) which surveyed (343) customers of a tourism company in Bandung, the results showed a significant impact of customer value on customer loyalty.

Studies Related to Brand Evangelism

Rehman's, (2022) study, which surveyed 245 students from three universities in Islamabad, concluded that brand commitment, identity, image, and trust significantly influence brand evangelism. It also confirmed the mediating role of emotional attachment in strengthening the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. (David's, 2022) study collected data from (606) graduates from (15) higher education institutions in Tanzania. The results revealed that most graduates engage in university brand evangelism when they are strongly connected to their university community. Furthermore, the results confirm that the highest level of evangelism is achieved through a sense of belonging to the university as a mediating variable. (Bin & Suaree's, 2023) study concluded that customers of the top five Malaysian telecom brands encourage others to try the brand and dissuade them from purchasing competing brands. (Osmanova's ,2023) study revealed that A study conducted on (323) Starbucks customers revealed that brand symbolism had the strongest impact on positive brand engagement, followed by purchase intention, as dimensions of brand evangelism. (Purohit,2023, 2) revealed that hotel customer engagement is a necessary condition for brand evangelism. (Asan ,2024) aimed to investigate the influence of individual factors such as environmental self-identity and brand-related factors such as association and trust with the green brand on brand evangelism, with green brand experience acting as a mediator in these relationships. Data was collected from (404) respondents through a questionnaire, and the results of the study confirmed the achievement of the study objectives.

Research Gap

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Research

A review of previous studies reveals the following two research gaps, which the current research seeks to fill:

A. Knowledge Gap: The current research provides innovative knowledge linking two variables that had not previously been directly addressed.

B. Spatial Gap: The spatial gap was represented by the fact that the research was conducted in the field of restaurant services, a field of importance that had not been previously researched in any local or Arab environment.

Building Research Hypotheses

Brand evangelism entails actively supporting the brand as a product or organization, including Positive Brand Referral about it, the intent to purchase or continue to engage with the brand, and Oppositional Brand Referral about competing brands. For customer behavior to occur through brand evangelism, the customer must be provided with functional, emotional, and symbolic customer value. Three hypotheses were adopted regarding the relationship between customer value types and each brand evangelism behavior:

Functional Value and Brand Evangelism

There is a positive and significant relationship between customer value, in its three forms, and positive branding of a customer's favorite restaurant. The increase in customer functional value, achieved through several elements, includes offering a diverse range of services of appropriate quality, Speed of service, reasonable prices, offering discounts and gifts, and listening to and quickly resolving complaints. These values, and many others, are perceived by customers and will further encourage them to speak positively about their preferred brand (Bernart et al., 2024, 6). This will also generate an intention to continue purchasing from the organization in the short term. According to (Korea et al., 2021), the functional benefits provided by a service have an impact on consumer purchasing behavior, as functional benefits are linked to the intention to continue purchasing or dealing with the organization in the future (Latifa &Hidayat , 2024, 84). He may develop a desire to speak inappropriately about competing brands or refuse to try, buy, or recommend them (Guo & Weiping, 2022, 20949).

Emotional Values and Brand Evangelism Behaviors

If a customer feels pleasure, happiness, satisfaction, and security when experiencing a service, receives functional benefits, and has a pleasant experience (Nicholson, 2021, 106), in addition to respecting customers, welcoming them, willingness to help them, and dedication to service, this will generate trust in the service and the organization providing it. This will lead to enhanced positive customer feelings, which in turn impacts positive word-of-mouth that customers generate about their preferred service and recommend it to others. This will increase the likelihood of repurchasing from the service in the future (Hiray & Anjum, 2022, 3001). A study conducted by (Yayla &Cengiz, 2007), revealed a positive relationship between customer emotional value and positive Brand Referral (Pedreno & Garcia, 2022, 54). According to (Padungyos et al. 2020), there is a positive and significant relationship between emotional value and purchase intention. An increase in perceived emotional values will encourage a positive and significant increase in the customer's intention to continue purchasing or dealing with the organization (Bernarto et al., 2024, 7).

Customer who receives customer values that satisfy his emotional needs from an organization tends to consider it as one of the best organizations and does not see any other organization similar to it, despite this organization having the ability to provide him with the same benefits, if not more and better. This feeling resulting from the emotional relationship with that organization that the customer experiences will make him behave negatively towards competing organizations that provide the same service and he may provide negative information about them to others (Pedreno & Garcia, 2022, 54).

Symbolic Values and Brand Evangelism

Symbolic values or benefits serve as a means for customers to express their self, identity, and desired lifestyle. Self-verification theory suggests that consumers seek brand experiences that align with their self-concept as part of self-verification or self-esteem (Nazim, 2021, 3), leading them to speak positively about the brand (Gaule & Jovarauskiene, 2022, 5). Alternatively, a customer may be interested in knowing the social consequences of consuming or using a particular brand (Yen et al., 2014, 1476). They may desire appreciation, praise, or admiration from others, or achieve the social status they aspire to achieve within their social circle (Nazim, 2021, 3). They may also feel proud if others express positive opinions about the brand they consume or uses. Receiving symbolic benefits may prompt customers to speak positively about their favorite restaurant, as well as express negative feelings and behaviors toward competing brands, such as refraining from purchasing them or using undesirable phrases about them (Al-Sattouhi et al., 2024, 5), and urging others not to deal with or purchase them. Symbolic benefits relate to an individual's relationship with others and their interest in being influenced by or being influenced by them.

Based on the above, the researchers propose the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: Types of customer value influence positive Brand Referral behavior.

Hypothesis 2: Types of customer value influence Oppositional Brand Referral behavior.

Hypothesis 3: Types of customer value influence brand purchase intent.

Research Methodology

Research Methodology and Tool

The descriptive approach was used to review the theoretical aspect of previous literature related to the research topic, and the analytical approach was used to analyze the primary data collected from the questionnaire. The data was analyzed to test the research hypotheses using appropriate statistical methods to extract results and draw conclusions, in preparation for formulating recommendations that serve the research objectives. The questionnaire was formulated based on several studies, including: (Bernarto et al., 2024; Pedreno & Garcia, 2022; Latiefa & Hidayat, 2024; Gaule & Jovarauskiene, 2022; Kovanoviene et al., 2021).

The first part of the questionnaire included questions about the demographic information of the respondents, while the second part of the questionnaire included questions related to the research variables. A three-point Likert scale was adopted (1 = disagree, 2 = neutral, 3 = agree).

Research Sample

The research sample consisted of customers who frequented three famous restaurants in Mosul, which were chosen as the research area: (Hatab, Khattar, and Abu Laila). Given the large size of the research community, the lack of a specific framework, and the time and cost constraints surrounding the research, the researchers used a simple random sample whose size was determined according to the equation (Green, 1991).

$$n > 50 + 8(P) \quad (1)$$

Because

P: Number of dimensions of independent variables (3)

n= Sample size

$n \geq 50 + 8(3)$

$n \geq 50 + 24$

$n \geq 74$

According to the equation outputs, the minimum sample size should be greater than (74) customers. Therefore, the sample size will be expanded to (80) customers to represent the community more broadly. (80) questionnaires were distributed to actual customers present in the three selected restaurants, and (79) valid questionnaires were retrieved for statistical analysis. The distribution of the research sample according to personal characteristics can be illustrated in Table (1), which shows that male customers who are employees and in the age group (31-40) are the group that frequents restaurants the most. This is a natural thing that is consistent with the social environment of the Mosul community, which places restrictions on females visiting restaurants alone. Table (2) also shows that the number of times customers ate at the restaurant preferred by three times was the largest percentage, which indicates that restaurants seek to provide customers with types of customer values that motivate them to practice types of missionary behavior for the preferred brand.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristic

Demographic Factors	Categories	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	66	54.83
	Female	13	16.46
Occupation	student	12	1.67
	employee	46	85.27
	winer	12	1.67
	retired	9	11.39
Age	30 years and under	23	29.11
	31-40 years old	25	31.65
	41- 50 years old	16	20.25
	51 years and older	15	54.83
Number of times you visit the restaurant	Once	15	18.99
	Twice	10	12.66
	Three times	30	37.97
	Four times or more	24	30.38

Results

Analysis of Customer Responses Regarding Types of Customer Value and Brand Evangelism

This section presents and analyzes the responses of the customers who participated in the study, reflecting their views on the types of customer value and brand Evangelism behaviors. This section included presenting the arithmetic means and standard deviations, and determining the response rate for each of the research variables. According to the results presented in Table (2), the responses showed that the arithmetic means for the three types of customer value were higher than the hypothetical mean of (2), with relatively low standard deviations, with the exception of symbolic value, which was high. This indicates a relatively high dispersion in customer responses to this variable (a large variance in opinions), despite it having the highest arithmetic mean and the highest response rate. The responses to brand Evangelism behaviors also showed that their arithmetic means were higher than the hypothetical mean, with the exception of the mean for the variable of

Oppositional brand referral about Competing brands, which was below the hypothetical mean and had the lowest response rate compared to the other behaviors.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistic

No	variable	Mean	St. Dev.	Response rate %
Customer value				
1	Symbolic Value	2.46	1.22	82
2	Functional Value	2.45	0.50	81.67
3	Emotional Value	2.43	0.47	81
Brand Evangelism				
1	Positive brand referral	2.41	0.50	80.33
2	Purchase intention	2.30	0.53	76.67
3	Oppositional brand referral	1.77	0.52	59

Research Scale Evaluation

Partial structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) was used to verify the construct validity of the research scales and test the three research hypotheses. The tests included the following:

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is an indicator of the soundness of the research instrument (questionnaire)'s construction and content validity, or it is an expression of the validity of the hypothetical research model. (Croemer et al. 2021) presented an improved measure of discriminant validity using correlations between research dimensions, provided that its value does not exceed (0.85) to prove discriminant validity. Table (3) & (4), shows that the value of the correlation coefficients between the types of customer values, and the value of the correlation coefficients between brand evangelism behaviors were acceptable and did not exceed (0.85), which is an indication that the research scale is characterized by discriminant validity for measuring customer value and brand evangelism behaviors.

Table3. Discriminant Validity in Customer Value

Variable	Functional Value	Emotional Values	Symbolic value
Functional Value	-	0.58	0.36
Emotional Values	-	-	0.42

Table4. Discriminant Validity in Brand Evangelism

Variable	Positive brand referral	Oppositional brand referral	Purchase intention
Positive brand referral	-	0.14	0.67
Oppositional brand referral	-	-	0.02

Conformity quality indicators

This is a group of indicators shown in Table (5), according to which the model is accepted, modified, or rejected. If the data matches the model and is accepted, the scale is good and accurate.

Table 5. Standards Adopted for the Typical Quality of Research Variables

No	Indicator	Acceptance limits
1	Percentage (degrees of freedom) (MIN/ DF	Exact match to the assumed model if it is less than (2).
2	Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) of the theoretical model with the applied model	If it is less than (0.90) it means there is a weak match.
3	Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	If it is greater than (0.85) it means that there is an acceptable fit.
4	Standardized Conformity Index (NFI)	It indicates good model fit if it reaches (0.90) or more.
5	Economic Quality of Conformity Index (PGFI)	It indicates good model fit if it reaches (0.60) or more.
6	Root Mean Square Residuals (RMR)	It indicates a good fit of the model if it reaches (0.08) or less.
7	Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	The closer it gets to the correct one.

When conducting confirmatory factor analysis for the two research variables, the results in Table (6) showed that the value of (Chi2) for both variables was statistically significant at the level of (0.000). The value of (GFI) reached (0.70) and (0.76) for both variables, which is a goodness of fit index close to the value of one (perfect fit). In the same context, the corrected goodness of fit index (AGFI) reached (0.40) and (0.53), which indicates an acceptable fit. It was also shown that the standard fit index (NFI) for both variables was (1.000), indicating a good fit of the model. As for the economic goodness of fit index (PGFI), its value for both variables was (0.35) (0.38), indicating a good fit of the model. The value of the root mean square residuals (RMR) for both variables was (0.14) and (0.07), indicating a good fit of the model. Based on the previous results, the research model is good and accurate.

Table 6. Quality of Fit Indicators for Research Variables

Indicator	Value of customer value	Value of Brand Evangelism	Results
CMIN / DF	16.33 (0.00)	16.37 (0.00)	Exact match to the assumed model
GFI	0.70	0.76	Good match
AGFI	0.40	0.53	Acceptable Match
NFI	1.00	1.00	exact match
PGFI	0.35	0.38	Acceptable Match
RMR	0.14	0.07	Good match
CFI	1.00	1.00	exact match

Hypothesis Testing

Testing the first hypothesis: The three customer values that a restaurant provides to its customers influence their motivation to positive brand referral about the restaurant. The results are shown in Table (7).

Table 7. The Effect of Customer Value on Enhancing Positive Brand Referral

Hypothesis No.	In Depended variable		Depended variable	Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Decision
1	Functional Value	→	positive brand referral	0.17	0.73	2.27	0.02	Accept

	Emotional Value	→		0.80	0.81	9.98	0.00	Accept
	Symbolic value	→		0.004	0.03	-0.15	0.88	Reject
Indicator	Value		Result					
CMIN / DF	25.11 0.00		Exact match to the assumed model					
RMR	0.15		Weak matching					
GFI	0.52		Weak matching					
AGFI	0.20		Acceptable Match					
PGFI	0.31		Acceptable Match					
CFI	1.00		exact match					
NFI	1.00		exact match					

Testing the second hypothesis: The three customer values that a restaurant provides to its customers influence their motivation Oppositional brand Referral about competing restaurants. The results are shown in Table (8).

Table 8. The Effect of Customer Value on Enhancing Oppositional Brand Referral

Hypothesis No.	In Depended variable		Depended variable	Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Decision
2	Functional Value	→	Oppositional brand Referral	0.02-	0.14	-0.15	0.88	Rejected
	Emotional Values	→		0.17	0.16	.061	0.29	Rejected
	Symbolic value	→		-0.004	0.05	-0.07	0.94	Rejected
Indicator	Value		Result					
CMIN / DF	8.47 0.00		Exact match to the assumed model					
RMR	0.11		Weak matching					
GFI	0.75		Weak matching					
AGFI	0.58		Acceptable Match					
PGFI	0.45		Acceptable Match					
CFI	1.00		exact match					
NFI	1.00		exact match					

Testing the third hypothesis: The three customer values that a restaurant conveys to its customers influence their intention to repeat business with the restaurant. The results of the hypothesis test are shown in table(9).

Table 9. The Effect of Customer Value on Enhancing Intent to Continue Purchasing the Brand

Hypothesis No.	In Depended variable		Depended variable	Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Result
3	Functional Value	→	Intent to purchasing the brand	0.26	0.11	2.30	0.02	Accept
	Emotional Values	→		0.51	0.12	4.12	0.00	Accept
	Symbolic value	→		0.03	0.04	0.74	0.46	Rejected

Indicator	Value	Result
CMIN / DF	15.49 0.00	Exact match to the assumed model
RMR	0.15	Weak matching
GFI	0.58	Weak matching
AGFI	0.31	Acceptable Match
PGFI	0.35	Acceptable Match
CFI	1.00	exact match
NFI	1.00	exact match

Discussion of the Results

Discussing the Types of Customer Values Customers Receive from the Restaurants They Visit

Customer value is one of the successful business strategies in today's organizations. If they provide customers with a diverse and high-value offering that encompasses all types of customer value, this leads the organization to a leading position in the local and global market (McFarlane, 2013, 17). It plays a key role in analyzing customer behavior before and after purchase. It is the key to gaining a competitive advantage and remaining relevant in the market. It also plays a fundamental role in building positive customer attitudes toward the organization's products. According to the results of the descriptive statistics for the research variables, the restaurants surveyed succeeded in providing customers with the three values, although there was some variation in achieving this. Symbolic value ranked first, but there was a high variance among the responses. Customers have good relationships with restaurant staff and feel pride, respect, and self-esteem when they choose their favorite restaurant. Functional value ranked second. Customers perceive the restaurant they frequent as offering quality service at reasonable prices, prompt service delivery, and prompt resolution of any complaints. Emotional value ranked last. Customers feel that the food served at their favorite restaurants is delicious and healthy, and they feel happy that the service provided by the staff exceeds their expectations. Furthermore, their favorite restaurant offers all the amenities they need for a comfortable stay.

Discussing Restaurant Customers' Engagement in Brand Evangelism:

Brand evangelism has received significant attention in marketing literature in recent years. Given the tendency of brand evangelists to repurchase, spread positive information about the brand, and defend it when attacked, it is of key strategic importance for service organizations, particularly restaurants, in building a base of loyal customers, particularly in the face of intense competition. The results of the descriptive data analysis of the current study supported previous propositions. The results of this study were consistent with those of (Amani,2022)

Discussing the results of the impact of customer values on Enhancing evangelistic behavior:

Knowing the impact of any marketing variable on another is a priority for organizations. This way, the organization is prepared to anticipate and react to potential changes, according to a pre-determined strategy that predicts the impact of any marketing variable as an independent variable on each of the dependent variables (Pedreno & Garcia, 2022, 51). This study aims to contribute to the brand marketing literature by providing a conceptual overview of the marketing variables that predict customer value. This work demonstrates that perceived customer value is necessarily achieved if customers are provided with various types of values (functional, emotional, and symbolic). In times of high competitiveness, customer value, in its various forms, is a crucial element in customers' adoption of brand evangelism behavior (Pedreno & Garcia, 2022, 51). To enhance customer evangelism at a higher rate, customers should be provided with various types of

customer value. The field results of the current research showed that the evangelistic behavior of the restaurant customers studied can be stimulated by providing them with certain types of customer value. The emotional and functional value customers receive had an effect on encouraging them to speak positively about their favorite restaurant and their intention to revisit the restaurant, both of which contribute to brand evangelism. When a customer feels happy, secure, and amazed by the quality and affordability of the services provided, the promptness with which they respond to customer concerns, the food being healthy and delicious, the comfort amenities provided, and the dedication of the staff to serving the customer, these values will prompt the customer to spread positive word about the restaurant they have visited. They will also talk to their friends and invite them to visit their favorite restaurant.

Furthermore, the customer will desire to eat at their favorite restaurant in the near future, which provides good service and offers the best food. The results of the current study did not reveal any incentive or desire on the part of customers to speak negatively about competing restaurants. This may be due to customers' adherence to ethical and religious standards in not defaming competing restaurants. Customers were satisfied with the emotional and functional value they derive from their favorite restaurants, which they frequent. The results of this study were partially consistent with the results of a study by (Pedreno & Madariaga,2022), as symbolic values did not significantly influence the intention to revisit a favorite restaurant. The results of the current study differed from those of (Osmanova,2023), as symbolic values had a positive impact on motivating customers to speak positively about the brand in this study.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This research sought to verify the important role played by three types of customer value (functional, emotional, and symbolic) in enhancing the evangelistic behavior of customers who frequent their favorite restaurants that provide them with these types of value. Primary data was collected from a sample of customers who frequented three restaurants selected for the field study in this research.

The results of the current research confirm the positive effects of functional and emotional values, which customers acquire in evangelizing a restaurant brand through positive brand referral and the desire to continue dealing with the brand and receiving its services. The research confirms the pivotal role of these two values in brand evangelistic behavior, demonstrating their strategic importance in achieving excellence and customer retention. Based on the research results, this research provides administrative contributions (suggestions) for restaurant owners and managers by drawing their attention to the importance of customer value as a strategic option that is primarily linked to the marketing function as one of the important activities of organizations concerned with delivering value to the customer and gaining value from him, which has a direct and effective impact on making customers advocates and evangelists for the restaurant brand, supporters and defenders of it, and the continuity of dealing with it and preventing their leakage to competing restaurants as long as the restaurant continues to provide them with the distinguished value that achieves a combination of benefits and that outperforms its competitors. Therefore, when hospitality service providers seek to create value and deliver it to the customer, they seek to influence the restaurant's evangelistic behavior among customers who obtain the value.

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